

Multi-beam Optical Beamformer PICs for LiDAR and RADAR Applications

(Invited paper)

Dimitra Ketzaki¹, Ronis Maximidis¹, Stephanos Kovaivos^{1,2}, Apostolos Tsakiridis¹, Miltiadis Moralis-Pegios¹, Nikolaos Pleros^{1,2}

¹Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

e-mail: dketzaki@auth.gr

ABSTRACT

The optical beamformers that rely on Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) have emerged as highly reliable alternatives compared to the bulky and energy-hungry RF chains and mechanical steering systems. Stemming from the rapid penetration of PIC technologies into both the radiofrequency (RF) and the free-space optics (FSO) application areas, Optical Multi-beam Beamformer Network (OMBFN) architectures have been demonstrated as a solution to the inevitable increase of the radiating elements when a single antenna array is employed for the generation of multiple beams. So far, these architectures rely primarily on the adaptation of network solutions developed for RF implementation, most prevalent to be Butler or Blass matrices. These solutions, however, come with their disadvantages supporting either static beams distribution or preventing every beam from being generated and steered independently. In this work, we present the exploitation of the crossbar (Xbar)-based universal linear operator as an OMBFN, offering the independent generation and control of multiple simultaneous beams.

Keywords: Optical Beam forming, Cross-bar architecture, multi-beam optical network.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last years, the impressive advancement on the on-going global race for highly automated or autonomous vehicles [1] is setting the stage for major transformations across the transportation industry. Transforming, however, the technological concepts into a tangible reality can be proven more challenging than originally anticipated [2] since recent studies urgently call for a new generation of integrated, cost-effective and multi-domain sensory systems [3]. Photonics-based LiDAR and microwave-photonic RADAR implementations have been identified as key enabling technologies for next generation sensing systems, due to their cost, size and energy profits, along with their increased frequency operational bandwidth translating into high range resolution [4]. Delving deeper, however, into the recently demonstrated photonic-assisted LiDAR and RADAR prototypes [5], [6] reveals some fundamental shortcomings towards next-generation high-performance sensor solutions mostly stemming from the lack of a solid development roadmap for multi-beam beamforming capabilities in LiDAR and RADAR implementations. In this sense, the small number of optical Multi-Beam Beamformer Network (MBFN) approaches proposed so far are mimicking respective RF circuit topologies, like Blass [7], Nolen [8] and Butler matrix layouts [9], significantly impacting the reconfigurability and the accumulated phase error of the resulting circuitry, while maintaining a tight interdependence of the applied phase values. These architectures spill over to the functional capabilities of the demonstrations, marking multi-beam implementations as extremely challenging and failing to harness the optical MBFN advantages in generating same quality beams in terms of Side-Lobe-Level, beamwidth and Equivalent Isotropic Radiated Power. For this reason, distinct sensor deployments for LiDAR and RADAR systems are still dominating the photonic sensor-based landscape, hampering their well-known synergies and complementarity that can offer fail-safe and weather condition agnostic environmental data [10] and necessitating the parallel design and deployment of different technologies [11].

Within this work an agile, low-cost and energy-efficient multi-sensor platform is launched that will re-architect the photonic-sensor domain and deliver heterogeneous information fusion and enhanced environmental perception by combining a multibeam LiDAR and a multibeam photonic-assisted RADAR within a single synthetic vision package.

2. MULTI-SENSOR SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Reaping the benefits of the best-in-class material platforms, technologies and architectures the system proposed herein brings together the recently demonstrated linear optical circuit topologies [12], transferring their credentials onto the SiN platform for upgrading photonic beamformers into MBFN layouts and demonstrating a whole new class of MBFN PICs suitable for microwave, mmWave and optical sensors. This unique combination of technological innovations will allow a full-fledged portfolio of LiDAR and RADAR sensors fused optimally into a powerful LiDAR and RADAR multi-sensor system. Figure 1 illustrates a pictorial view of the envisioned multi-sensor system.

Figure 1. LiDAR and RADAR multi-sensor system

3. MULTI-BEAM OPTICAL BEAMFORMER NETWORK

To demarcate from traditional optical MBFN attempts that have so far emphasized in mimicking respective RF BFN topologies like Blass [7], [13], Nolen [8] and Butler [9] matrix layouts, this work will deploy an underlying MBFN technology that can be easily adapted along the needs of microwave/mmWave RADARs and LiDARs. In this way, the proposed system will overcome the traditional RF MBFN matrix shortcomings *i.e.* the absence or highly complex reconfigurability [14], the non-negligible phase errors [15]-[19], and the tight interdependence of phase values that stems from the employment of cascaded matrix nodes[20], leading to a disruptive MBFN PIC portfolio that can be widely adopted in both RADAR/LiDAR application segments.

To achieve its goals the system proposed herein will proceed along a novel $N \times M$ linear optical circuit architecture relying on a photonic Xbar configuration, that has been recently formulated theoretically [12], [21] and experimentally validated as matrix-vector multiply engine reported in the area of neuromorphic photonics [22], [23]. The photonic Xbar linear optical architecture relies on a coherent multiport interferometer and is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2(a) when configured to operate within a single-wavelength, with the input vector formed by an array of parallel modulation stages located directly after a 1:N front-end splitter stage.

Figure 2.a) The photonic Xbar architecture, b) the experimental setup utilized for the optical characterization of the 4×4 Xbar, c)-d) observed and predicted optical power of as a function of the achievable steering angle for two Xbar beams B1,B2.

The 1:N splitter followed by the N modulators provides N parallel optical beams that get subsequently launched into the Xbar matrix, with every beam entering through a respective waveguide row. Each of the rows employs an optical coupling stage at every of the matrix columns, so that part of the modulated optical beam gets forwarded into the respective column, while the remaining part is allowed to continue to the next column. The intra-column beams are then entering respective Variable Amplitude and Phase (VAP) modulation blocks, termed as Xbar nodes, with each of them comprising an optical amplitude modulator followed by a phase modulator, allowing in this way the amplitude and phase adjustment of the propagating beam. After exiting the Xbar node, the intra-column optical beams are then forced to coherently recombine in a N:1 recombination stage that comprises a binary tree of optical couplers, following the principles that have been described in [24], [12]. This leads to the radiation of a sum of N amplitude and phase-modulated signals from every i^{th} column. These

radiated signals - by each column- will coherently add over-the-air generating as many beams as the number of input signals.

In simple terms, the Xbar layout naturally extends the successful and powerful 1:M Optical Phase Array (OPA) paradigm into a NxM Optical Amplitude and Phase Matrix (OAPM) configuration through an overall 1:M splitting of the input modulated beams and the use of N:1 recombination stages within every column, without requesting the employment of N different wavelengths and WDM technology for expanding to N rows, as has been the case in [25]. This allows for an optical MBFN technology where one-to-one mapping between intended beam amplitude/phase adjustment values and respective Xbar matrix node entry is supported, avoiding phase interdependencies and unnecessary recalculations. At the same time a completely reconfigurable amplitude and phase matrix can be sustained with zero phase errors and additional beam shaping capabilities can be supported, since the capability to host VAP modulation blocks instead of simple phase modulation elements can utilize the amplitude modulation segments for significantly facilitating side lobe suppression [26]. Finally, a high loss- and phase-induced fidelity architecture is supported [7], enabling a robust circuit layout where a perfect match between the targeted and the experimentally obtained linear transformation can be accomplished.

The Xbar-based MBFN topology has been also experimentally validated for its beam steering capabilities [27] on a MBFN built on a SiPho 4x4 Xbar chip (Fig.2(b)). Figures 2(c) and 2(d) show the experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated Xbar optical power corresponding to the identified steering angles, for two generated beams B1 and B2 respectively, validating the multibeam operation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the exploitation of the crossbar (Xbar)-based universal linear operator as an OMBFN, offering the independent generation and control of multiple simultaneous beams. A Xbar-based OMBFN chip has been evaluated proving the proposed topology beam handling capabilities towards a new class of MBFN PICs that can be suitable for microwave, mmWave and optical sensors by uniquely combining its technological innovations aiming at a full-fledged portfolio of LiDAR and RADAR sensors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the EU through the HORIZON project PARALIA (PN: 101093013).

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://www.wevolver.com/article/2020.autonomous.vehicle.technology.report> [Online]
- [2] <https://archive.thinkprogress.org/top-toyota-expert-truly-driverless-cars-might-not-be-in-my-lifetime-Occa05ab19ff/> [Online]
- [3] J. A. Baxtere et. al., "Review of Electrical Architectures and Power Requirements for Automated Vehicles," 2018 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference and Expo (ITEC).
- [4] B. Gao et. al., "High-resolution phased array radar imaging by photonics-based broadband digital beamforming," *Opt. Express* 27, 13194-13203 (2019).
- [5] Zhang, F., Guo, Q. & Pan, S. Photonics-based real-time ultra-high-range-resolution radar with broadband signal generation and processing. *Sci Rep* 7, 13848 (2017).
- [6] S. A. Miller et. al., "Large-scale optical phased array using a low-power multi-pass silicon photonic platform," *Optica* 7, 3-6 (2020).
- [7] J. Blass, "Multidirectional antenna: A new approach to stacked beams", in *Proc. IRE Int. Conv. Rec.*, 1960, vol. 8, pp. 48-50.
- [8] J. Nolen, "Synthesis of multiple beam networks for arbitrary illuminations", Ph.D. dissertation, Radio Division, endix Corp., Baltimore, MD, USA, Apr. 1965.
- [9] J. Butler et. al., "Beam-forming matrix simplifies design of electronically scanned antennas", *Electron. Des.*, vol. 9, 1961.
- [10] F. Scotti, et. al., "Multi-Frequency Lidar/Radar Integrated System for Robust and Flexible Doppler Measurements," in *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 27, no. 21, pp. 2268-2271, 1 Nov.1, 2015.
- [11] F. Scotti et al., "Microwave photonics for Integrated multifrequency lidar / radar system," *Opto-Electronics and Communications Conference (OECC)*, 2015.
- [12] G. Giamougiannis et. al., "Coherent photonic crossbar as a universal linear operator", submitted to *Laser and Photonics Review* (2021).
- [13] C. Tsokos et al., "Analysis of a Multibeam Optical Beamforming Network Based on Blass Matrix Architecture," in *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 36, no. 16, pp. 3354-3372, 15 Aug, (2018).
- [14] Y. J. Guo, et. al. "Circuit Type Multiple Beamforming Networks for Antenna Arrays in 5G and 6G Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks," in *IEEE Journal of Microwaves*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 704-722, July 2021

- [15] H. Ren, et. al., "Ultra-compact 3×3 Nolen matrix beamforming network," *IET Microw. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 14, 2020
- [16] H. Ren, et. al., "A novel design of 4 x 4 butler matrix with relatively flexible phase differences," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 15, pp. 1277-1280, 2016.
- [17] T. Djerafi et. al., "Planar Ku -Band 4× 4 Nolen Matrix in SIW Technology," in *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 259-266, Feb. 2010.
- [18] G. A. Adamidis et. al., "Design and implementation of single-layer 4x4 and 8x8 butler matrices for multibeam antenna arrays," *Int. J. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 2019, pp. 1-12, Mar. 2019.]
- [19] P. Chen et. al., "A Double Layer Substrate Integrated Waveguide Blass Matrix for Beamforming Applications," in *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 374-376, June 2009
- [20] Y. Aslan, et. al. "Orthogonal Versus Zero-Forced Beamforming in Multibeam Antenna Systems: Review and Challenges for Future Wireless Networks," in *IEEE Journal of Microwaves*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 879-901, Oct. 2021
- [21] M. Moralis-Pegios et. al., "Neuromorphic Silicon Photonics and Hardware Deep Learning for High-Speed Inference", *JLT* (2022).
- [22] G. Dabos et. al., "Neuromorphic photonic technologies and architectures: Scaling opportunities and performance frontiers", *Optical Mat. Express* (2022).
- [23] M. Moralis Pegios et. al., "Photonic Neuromorphic Computing: Architectures, Technologies, and Training Models", 2022 *Optical Fiber Communications (OFC)*, M1G.4, (2022).
- [24] G. Mourgias-Alexandris et al., "Neuromorphic Photonics With Coherent Linear Neurons Using Dual-IQ Modulation Cells," in *J. of Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 811-819, 15 Feb.15, 2020.
- [25] C. Tsokos, et al. "Optical Beamforming Network for Multi-Beam Operation With Continuous Angle Selection." *PTL* (2019).
- [26] R. Mailloux, *Phased Array Antenna Handbook*. Norwood, MA, USA: Artech House, 2005.
- [27] S. Kovaïos et al. "An integrated multi-beam optical beamformer architecture with beam-shaping capabilities," 49th European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC 2023) 1414-1417, 10.1049/icp.2023.2573.